

Demographic Questionnaire

- Job title / role
- Years of professional experience / years at the company
- Neurodivergence
- Time since diagnosis
- Gender

General Instructions

The following questions refer exclusively to your experiences in the workplace, considering your current (or most recent) experiences as a technology professional. Please respond based on the frequency or intensity with which each statement represents your reality at work.

Neurodivergent Dysfunctions at Work [D]

Scale:

- 1 – Never
 - 2 – Rarely
 - 3 – Sometimes
 - 4 – Frequently
 - 5 – Always
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Inhibitory Control [D1]

- I make impulsive comments and later realize I should not have said them [D11];
- I interrupt other people while they are speaking, unintentionally [D12];
- I have difficulty controlling myself when I feel frustrated at work [D13];
- I do things without thinking about the consequences [D14];
- I have intense reactions when things do not happen as I expected [D15];
- I have difficulty maintaining composure when I am contradicted [D16].

Working Memory [D2]

- I forget information that I have just received at work [D21];
- I have difficulty remembering instructions that were given to me verbally [D22];
- I forget tasks that I was assigned to do [D23];
- I lose my train of thought in the middle of a conversation or task [D24];
- I need to write everything down because I do not trust my short-term memory [D25];
- I frequently forget important deadlines or commitments [D26].

Cognitive Flexibility [D3]

- I have difficulty switching tasks when something unexpected happens [D31];
- I feel uncomfortable when I need to deviate from my routine at work [D32];
- I become disorganized when there are many last-minute changes [D33];
- I have difficulty adapting my approach when something does not work [D34];
- I need more time than others to deal with changes [D35].

Workplace Accommodations [A]

Scale:

- 1 – Strongly disagree
- 2 – Disagree
- 3 – Neutral
- 4 – Agree
- 5 – Strongly agree

Institutional and Emotional Support [A1]

- The organization genuinely cares about my well-being [A11];
 - Even if I made a serious mistake, the organization would continue to support me [A12];
 - The organization would help me if I had a personal problem [A13];
 - I am confident that the organization would do its best to support me [A14];
 - The organization makes an effort to maintain my job satisfaction [A15].
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Organizational Sensitivity to Individual Needs [A2]

- The organization takes my personal goals and values into account [A21];
 - When changes occur, the organization is concerned about how they affect me [A22];
 - The organization is open to discussing my specific needs [A23].
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Fairness and Human Treatment [A3]

- I feel that I can trust the organization [A31];
 - The organization treats me fairly [A32];
 - The organization treats me as a human being, not just as a number [A33];
 - The organization shows little interest in me [A34];
 - The organization ignores my professional interests [A35].
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Professional Appreciation [A4]

- The organization values my contribution [A41];
 - The organization recognizes when I do a good job [A42].
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Openness to Dialogue and Listening [A5]

- The organization considers my opinion to be relevant [A51].

Individual Work-Related Journey [J]

Scale:

- 1 – Never
 - 2 – Rarely
 - 3 – Sometimes
 - 4 – Frequently
 - 5 – Always
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State Regulation [J1]

- I have difficulty starting my tasks even when I know they are important [J11];
 - I experience sudden drops in energy during the workday [J12];
 - I feel unproductive for long periods, even when I have time available [J13];
 - I postpone tasks until the last moment, even when they are simple [J14];
 - I have difficulty maintaining a consistent work pace throughout the day [J15];
 - I feel that my productivity depends on my mood [J16].
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Delay Aversion [J2]

- I become very impatient when I have to wait for responses or decisions [J21];
- I feel anxious when I do not see immediate progress on tasks [J22];
- I have difficulty working on long-term projects [J23];
- I become easily frustrated when I need to wait for other people [J24];
- I lose interest when results take too long to appear [J25].

Perceptions of Your Work Performance [P]

Scale:

- 1 – Never
 - 2 – Rarely
 - 3 – Sometimes
 - 4 – Frequently
 - 5 – Always
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Task Performance [P1]

- I planned my work so that I completed it on time [P11];
 - I kept in mind the results I needed to achieve [P12];
 - I was able to set priorities [P13];
 - I performed my work efficiently [P14];
 - I managed my time well [P15].
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Contextual Performance [P2]

- On my own initiative, I started new tasks when I finished previous ones [P21];
 - I took on challenging tasks when they were available [P22];
 - I kept my professional knowledge up to date [P23];
 - I kept my work skills up to date [P24];
 - I proposed creative solutions to new problems [P25];
 - I took on extra responsibilities [P26];
 - I continuously sought new challenges at work [P27];
 - I actively participated in meetings and/or consultations [P28].
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Counterproductive Work Behavior [P3]

- I exaggerated the seriousness of minor problems at work [P31];
- I focused on the negative aspects of work situations rather than the positive ones [P32];
- I talked with colleagues about negative aspects of my work [P33];
- I spoke with people outside the organization about negative aspects of my work [P34];
- I complained about minor work-related problems [P35].